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Global Players in Transition: A Comparative Analysis of Peacekeeping Strategies by the USA and Russia with Focus on the Middle East Region

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Abstract

This research paper scrutinizes the shifts in peacekeeping and building strategies, with a specific focus on the contrasting approaches adopted by the United States and Russia in relation to the Middle East.

Historically, these two states have represented two powerful yet distinct blocs, each supporting opposite ideologies and forming different alliances. Although both are permanent members of the UNSC (United Nations Security Council), they have demonstrated dissimilar approaches to peacekeeping on national and global scales. While the United States' 'liberal' strategies are widely deemed to be "doomed to fail," after the collapse of the former Soviet Union (USSR), Russia, leading the non-Western bloc, appears to be taking an alternate avenue in a newly unipolar world. The communist state is not only acknowledged but also applauded by many for its "cultural triangulation." Its reputation amongst Eurasian states has mainly been positive. Having taken the lead in a manifold of successful interventions, "neutral states" have displayed a shift of support in favor of non-Western states rather than the "Collective West." For instance, the success may be substantiated via the Russian Federation involving many Asian states in the impact-making. For example, along with China, Russia works on improving the socio-economic situation in African countries.

Hence, against the backdrop of evolving geopolitical dynamics, this study employs a comprehensive comparative analysis to elucidate the divergent paths undertaken by these two major powers, focusing on their interventions in the Middle East region. More particularly, this paper will study how the public perceives their peacekeeping strategies regarding the latest developments in the Palestinian-Israeli conflict through an online survey.

Chapter I: Introduction

Background

Post-World War II, the United Nations (UN) and the UN Security Council (UNSC), according to Article 24 of the UN Charter, hold primary responsibility for maintaining international peace and security, authorizing peacekeeping operations to address global threats. Operating as an instrument of collective power politics, peacekeeping reflects the dominant perceptions of international security challenges. The permanent members of the UNSC, particularly during the Cold War, played a crucial role in shaping these perceptions. The dissolution of the Warsaw Pact and subsequent geopolitical shifts in the 1990s and 2000s altered the landscape, leading to the quasi-global influence of NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) as a representative of the "Collective West." This period, marked by the "unipolar moment," witnessed a distortion of peacekeeping principles, with the UN becoming an element of the structural power of the Collective West.

Additionally, on an international scale, the UN Security Council is primarily responsible for maintaining world peace, particularly after World War II. This alludes to taking whatever measures deemed necessary to achieve this objective. The decision maker, nevertheless, has always been a variable.

During the Cold War, bipolarity in politics came to life with the rise of the USA and the USSR, who created two robust defense systems through an arms race. Each was supported and legitimized by their bloc and UN allies. After the collapse of the USSR in the late 1990s, the non-Western bloc lost the power it once held, affecting the new

international agreements revolving around peacekeeping. Consequently, Western influence expanded along with liberal interventionism. A “multipolar world” emerged amid the “Collective West” era, transforming the UN into a multilateral force of the “Collective West.”

Recent years have seen a dramatic shift in the global balance of power, signaling a transition from the "Collective West" to the "Collective Non-West," notably with the ‘re-rise’ of Russia. This geopolitical transformation marks a "post-liberal moment in UN peacekeeping." The paper aims to explore the conceptual foundations of this shift, particularly in non-Western peacekeeping, focusing on the interventions in the Middle East. Briefly, this section investigates a timeline for such interventions. Starting in the late 1890s, the Zionist movement emerged, driven by Jews in Russia seeking a Jewish state after facing persecution. Subsequently, the movement gained momentum, leading to the first Zionist Congress in Switzerland in 1897, where a petition was made to allocate land for Jews in Palestine. Following World War I, the Ottoman Empire collapsed, with Britain taking control of Palestine.

In 1917, the Balfour Declaration was issued, expressing the aim to establish a Jewish state in Palestine. The year 1948 marked the establishment of Israel. Under President Truman's leadership, the USA was among the first countries to recognize it. Notably, Russia, under Stalin's rule, also officially recognized Israel three days after its declaration. In 1978, President Carter facilitated the Camp David Accords for peace. The USA focused on strategic diplomacy during this period, while the Soviet Union supported the Palestinian cause. In the Gulf War of 1991, the USA fought against Iraq, whereas Russia, in transition, condemned Iraq under Gorbachev. Following the events of 9/11, the Bush Doctrine outlined an anti-terror campaign. Russia expressed sympathy and signed the Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty in 2002. In the post-9/11 Afghanistan scenario, the USA addressed the Taliban and engaged in the war against terrorism, whereas Russia diplomatically engaged with Afghan factions. Subsequently, in the Syrian Civil War in 2011, the USA condemned the Syrian government's actions and conducted airstrikes against ISIS. In contrast, Russia intervened militarily in support of the Assad government.

These historical events demonstrate the contrasting approaches of the USA and Russia in the Middle East, with the former often emphasizing strategic diplomacy and military intervention and the latter maintaining diplomatic engagement and support for certain regional actors. Additionally, outlining this timeline helps illustrate the relentless changes

in approaches toward diplomacy and peacemaking by the two powerful blocs throughout the years.

Significance and Purpose of the Project

The topic of peacekeeping has resurfaced lately due to recent events in the Middle East, which shook the public opinion of individuals worldwide. On October 7, 2023, an unprecedented attack took place, triggering a war declared by Israel on Hamas, an Islamist militant movement against the occupier, with retaliatory bombings on Gaza. This paper will dive deep into the contributions of the USA, Russia, and the UN, naming the actions to which they have been each contributing as a response to this ongoing conflict.

Research questions

It is undeniable that the transition in power from being in the palm of the “Collective West” to the Russian sphere had taken place. This paper will attempt to explore the public perception of each of these powers in handling the latest Palestinian-Israeli conflict by answering the following two questions:

1. How would people evaluate the peacekeeping intervention of the USA?
2. How would people evaluate Russia's peacekeeping intervention?

Chapter II: Literature Review

A cross-reference with older publications on the matter is essential. Examining what studies showed about them is crucial to further investigate the research questions presented in this paper. While writing this paper, an article titled “Non-Western Peacekeeping as a Factor of a Multipolar World: Outlines of Research Program” by Adu, Y. N., Bokeriya, S. A., Degterev, D. A., Mezyaev, A. B., & Shamarov, P. V. (2023), was the starting point. Nevertheless, other sources are employed throughout the paper to create a solid foundation for this research.

Evolution of US Peacekeeping Approaches:

In the evolution of US peacekeeping approaches in the Middle East, particularly in the context of the Palestine-Israel conflict, the US formulated distinct doctrines. Historically, the Collective West has played a fundamental role in shaping peacekeeping efforts in the region, often aligning its strategies with broader geopolitical objectives. For instance, the post-World War II era witnessed the emergence of the US as a critical player in the establishment of the state of Israel in 1948. Subsequently, US involvement in the region evolved during the Cold War, with the superpower dynamics influencing peacekeeping initiatives. President Jimmy Carter's 1978 Camp David Accords marked a notable diplomatic milestone, showcasing the US commitment to mediating conflicts in the Middle East (via the USA Department of State, Office of Historians).

Moreover, the post-Cold War period brought about shifts in US approaches, with interventions in the Gulf War and later engagements in Iraq and Afghanistan illustrating a more assertive role. The US engagement in the Middle East has also been characterized by the articulation of doctrines such as the Carter Doctrine and the Bush Doctrine, each reflecting distinct perspectives on the role of the US in the region. Additionally, through its participation in various peacekeeping missions and contributions to international organizations, the United States has significantly influenced the development of global peacekeeping norms.

An Ongoing Cold War

This section dives into the slow transition in influence and power dynamics in the context of peacekeeping. The world became skeptical of the effectiveness of American

humanitarian interventions since the formation of a unipolar world. Even Americans tend to lack trust in their government as “fully 84% believe the level of confidence Americans have in the federal government can be improved” (Rainie et al. 2019). After the collapse of the USSR in 1991, Western power expanded along with liberal interventionism. A multipolar world emerged amid the “Collective West” era. UN peacekeeping budgets peaked in 2012 (UN Department of Public Information, 2012). These factors indicated a potential rise in efforts to maintain world peace, or at least those were the expectations. The aftermath was an increase in power but a decrease in impact. A pragmatic peacekeeping led to the “power vacuum” (University of Notre Dame, 2023), which happened gradually, first in Eurasia, when the US troops left Afghanistan, Syria, and Iraq. Additionally, no significant peacekeeping operation took place by the UN after 2014.

Russia’s Emergence as a Peacekeeping Actor

Russia's emergence as a peacekeeper in the Middle East, notably within the framework of the Palestine-Israel conflict, has been a multifaceted process driven by leveraging diplomatic influence and pursuing economic interests. For example, the annexation of Crimea in 2014 and subsequent strained relations with the West prompted Russia to diversify its international partnerships, leading to increased involvement in regions traditionally influenced by Western powers. Russia strategically positioned itself as a critical mediator and partner in the Middle East, seeking to capitalize on historical and regional alliances. Diplomatically, Russia has engaged in a series of initiatives to address the Palestine-Israel conflict, emphasizing a “multi-vector approach” that combines international forums (treaties) and direct negotiations. Additionally, Moscow's military interventions in the Syrian conflict have further solidified its presence and influence in the region (Smagin, 2023). The factors facilitating Russia's peacekeeping involvement include its status as a permanent member of the UN Security Council, providing a status to assert its influence on global security matters. Specifically, in the Palestine-Israel conflict, Russia has advocated for a more balanced approach, distancing itself from the US stance and emphasizing multilateral negotiations (Huaxia, 2023). Understanding Russia's motivations, strategies, and the contextual factors shaping its peacekeeping role is essential for having a solid grasp of the evolving dynamics in the Middle East and the broader transition in peacekeeping influence.

Comparative Analysis of Peacekeeping Approaches

Comparing the similarities and differences of the United States and Russia reveals distinct tactics and diplomatic strategies employed by these major powers in the Middle East, particularly within the context of the Palestine-Israel conflict. Historically, the United States has often utilized a combination of military interventions as part of its regional peacekeeping strategies. Namely, the Gulf War in 1991 and subsequent engagements in Iraq and Afghanistan have showcased a tendency towards assertive, violent action. While attempting to destroy WMD (Weapons of Mass Destruction), the USA caused the death of 100,000 Iraqis (Council on Foreign Relations, 2023).

In contrast, Russia's approach to peacekeeping in the Middle East has emphasized a multilateral stance (Stepanova, 2016). Russia has leveraged its role as a permanent member of the UN Security Council to advocate for diplomatic solutions in the Palestine-Israel conflict, steering away from "unilateral" military interventions. The annexation of Crimea in 2014 and its intervention in Syria underscore Russia's commitment to regional stability through diplomatic channels (Dragoi, 2014). This comparative analysis aims to dissect the differences in tactics and prudent strategies between the US and Russia and assess their respective impacts on conflict resolution dynamics in the Middle East. Understanding these variations is crucial for delineating the evolving landscape of peacekeeping influence in the region.

Attempted Resolutions following 10/07

As a result of Hamas's attack on Israel on October 7, at least 16 Russian citizens lost their lives. However, Moscow refrained from directly condemning Hamas. Instead, President Vladimir Putin attributed the current Middle East crisis to US policies. He drew a comparison between Israel's blockade of Gaza and Nazi Germany's siege of Leningrad, a profoundly significant event in Russian history (Borshchevskaya, 2023). Considering these circumstances, Putin offered to mediate between Israel and the Palestinians. This incident highlights Russia's explicit alignment with the global south, as it actively seeks to undermine the U.S.-led liberal world order. Putin has previously asserted that this order is an "ugly neo-colonial system" on the brink of collapse in favor of a multipolar world (France24, 2023).

A couple of days after the attack, two draft resolutions, one proposed by the US and the other by Russia, both addressing the Israel-Palestine conflict, failed to pass in the UN Security Council. The US resolution, which demanded humanitarian pauses in Gaza,

condemned a Hamas attack on October 7 and called for the immediate release of hostages, received ten votes in favor but was vetoed by Russia, China, and the United Arab Emirates. Russia's draft resolution, calling for a humanitarian cease-fire, also did not garner enough votes, receiving four in favor, two against (including the US and the UK), and nine abstentions. This marks the fourth time in ten days that the Security Council has vetoed draft resolutions related to the Israel-Palestine situation (Gunerigok, 2023). As of November 14, 2023, in a session of the Second Committee, three resolutions were approved, including one urging Israel to cease harming natural resources in the Occupied Palestinian Territory and the occupied Syrian Golan. The resolution, passed with 151 in favor, 6 against, and 11 abstentions, acknowledges the Palestinian people's right to seek restitution for resource exploitation by Israel. The Assembly expressed concern about the Israeli Air Force's destruction of oil storage tanks near the Lebanese Jiyah electric power plant in another resolution titled "Oil slick on Lebanese shores," approved by a vote of 158 in favor, 7 against, and 6 abstentions, with the United States voting against it. Various representatives, including those of Israel, the United States, and the United Kingdom, expressed dissatisfaction with resolutions, asserting bias against Israel. The Committee also approved a resolution related to Palestinian sovereignty, with the US and Israel voting against it, leading to further statements on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. The Israeli representative criticized the resolution for its one-sided nature. Iran criticized the Israeli regime's actions in Gaza, emphasizing the need for accountability and denouncing the international community's response. Right of Reply statements followed, with the State of Palestine rejecting claims of bias and Israel, Iran, and Pakistan engaging in reciprocal criticisms (United Nations, 2023).

Chapter III: Methodology

To ensure reliable findings to the above questions, scientific research necessitates valid research methods. For this project, a link to a survey in the format of Google Forms was forwarded to 3 group chats, not all centered around the American University of Beirut. Some groups involved Lebanese members, while others had a central Tunisian membership since I, the author, am from Tunisia. The deliberate choice of an online method is due to the need to target a large group of individuals from different ethnic, cultural, and religious backgrounds. Having diversity in mind while collecting quantitative data rationalizes this method's usage and procedure.

The link was sent on November 12, 2023, at 09:00 AM, and the ability to answer ended via stopping access to the link at 05:00 PM. By the end of the day, the sample size was medium, with 45 participants filling out the form. With no intention to deceive them, participants were welcomed with the following heading, giving away the aim of the study: "This survey aims to collect public opinions regarding the Oct 7 attacks of the ongoing conflict between Palestine and Israel. Hence, how would you assess the peacekeeping methods put into action thus far?"

Chapter IV: Results

The first question was whether the respondent was aware of the events on Oct 7, 2023, in the Middle East region. 95.6% answered yes, which was a reassuring foundation, knowing that the sample was not oblivious to the conflict, raising the likelihood of the results being reliable and valid.

The second question asked about the extent to which the respondent believes that international peacekeeping efforts have effectively resolved the recent conflict between Palestine and Israel in the Middle East. Notably, this question received, by far, the most diverse answers, with a mere 8.9% of respondents deeming these efforts as "effective to a large extent," highlighting a minority viewpoint. A slightly more significant portion, 13.3%, considered international peacekeeping "effective to some extent." However, the most predominant sentiment among respondents was skepticism, as an overwhelming 77.8% expressed the belief that international peacekeeping has been "ineffective in the slightest" in addressing the conflict.

The third question ranked on a scale from 1 to 5 the role played by the United States in resolving the recent conflict between Palestine and Israel. A significant majority of respondents, constituting 84.4%, rated the US role as "ineffective" by assigning a score of 1 on a scale from 1 to 5. Only a marginal percentage, 11.1%, offered a slightly more positive perspective by assigning a score of 2. An even smaller proportion, 2.2%, rated the US role as "effective" by selecting a score of 4, and an additional 2.2% regarded it as "very effective" with a score of 5.

Similarly, the fourth question assesses the role played by Russia in resolving the recent conflict between Palestine and Israel on a scale from 1 to 5. Most respondents, accounting for 62.2%, rated Russia's role as "ineffective," assigning a score of 1 on a scale from 1 to 5. A significant but smaller percentage, 20%, offered a moderately positive perspective with a score of 2. Additionally, 13.3% assigned a score of 3, indicating a belief in Russia's moderate effectiveness. A minor proportion, 4.4%, regarded Russia as "effective" by assigning a score of 4.

“In light of their opposing peacekeeping approaches in the Middle East conflict, how has your perception of the United States changed?” is the second to last question of the survey conducted and reflects distinct shifts in opinions. A significant majority, 73.3% of respondents, indicated their perception had "deteriorated." A notable but smaller proportion, 24.4%, reported that their perception remained "unchanged." A minimal 2.2% of respondents conveyed a positive shift, stating that their perception of the United States had "improved."

Lastly, the final question evaluated people’s perception of Russia based on their opposing peacekeeping approaches. 68.9% reported their perception of Russia remained "unchanged" despite the differing peacekeeping approaches. A smaller percentage, 17.8%, expressed that their perception had "deteriorated." Conversely, a minority of respondents, constituting 13.3%, conveyed a positive shift, stating that their perception of Russia had "improved."

These results are in alignment with Adu, Y. N., Bokeriya, S. A., Degterev, D. A., Mezyaev, A. B., & Shamarov, P. V., the authors of the article I used as a starting point. They share similarities regarding the public’s negative perception shifts towards the United States of America, specifically in the Middle East. According to the authors, the reason behind this transition is that the US’s humanitarian intervention there is doomed to fail since it was built on a problematic foundation. It has invested trillions of dollars in the military there. Hence, experts claim it is unwilling to take a democratic approach to create a positive change in states of conflict. They also suggested that the only solution to the liberal interventionism crisis is building upon the “UN support mission” by funding and supporting regional organizations, such as NGOs. That, too, is flawed due to the power imbalances within these ‘independent’ organizations.

Chapter V: Reflections

Conclusion

The striking disparity in responses in my survey underscores the complex nature of evaluating the efficacy of international peacekeeping endeavors in the Middle East, particularly concerning the Palestine-Israel conflict. The overwhelming majority of respondents expressing a lack of confidence in the effectiveness of these efforts suggests a widespread perception of shortcomings in the existing peacekeeping approaches. People are now seeing through these limitations. Moreover, the survey results point towards a sense of skepticism or dissatisfaction among respondents regarding the United States' contrasting peacekeeping approaches in the Middle East conflict. To analyze it, the substantial majority expressing a deterioration in perception suggests that the opposing strategies pursued by the US may have led to a decline in international approval. Furthermore, the mixed responses regarding Russia's role in the Palestine-Israel conflict showcase a nuanced perception among survey participants. While a majority expressed a lack of confidence in Russia's effectiveness, a sizable portion acknowledged varying degrees of positive impact.

As a key takeaway, this sentiment calls for critically examining current strategies. It highlights the necessity for comprehensive reassessment and potential restructuring of international peacekeeping mechanisms in the region. Acknowledging and addressing these divergent views is crucial for policymakers and international bodies aiming to contribute meaningfully to resolving conflicts in the Middle East, precisely that of Palestine.

Finally, after reflecting on the content cited above, it is tricky to answer the two initial questions of this research paper. The public perception of the United States of America and Russia varies from one era to another and from one state to another based on the geopolitical influence each holds. It is safe to deduct that there is a consensus on disagreeing with the USA's stance and resolution approach regarding the October 7 conflict between Israel and Hamas. Nevertheless, the majority appears neutral, even leaning toward agreeing with Russia's peacekeeping methods. One potential explanation for this could be the media's role in shaping people's perceptions by feeding them

different narratives. If there were only anecdotes of hostages all over the media, people would tend to sympathize with the victims and take Israel's side. However, social media platforms, such as Instagram and X (formerly known as Twitter), have been hosting a "free Palestine" movement ever since the news of the attack broke. Via sharing footage of Palestinian children buried under bombed hospitals, the users will lean into supporting Hamas and Russia and despising the USA for funding Israel.

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